

Solvent Extraction of Europium(III) and Neodymium(III) with 4(*p*)-Nitrobenzoyl-2,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one and Neutral Oxo-donors

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The mechanism of the extraction of europium(III) and neodymium(III) from aqueous buffer media with 4(*p*)-nitrobenzoyl-2,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one (NMPP) in toluene has been investigated. The value of $\log K_{ex}$ (where K_{ex} refers to the equilibrium $M^{3+} + 3HL \rightleftharpoons ML_3 + 3H^+$) is -1.4 and -1.6 for Eu and Nd respectively. NMPP seems to be superior to the corresponding 4-benzoyl-2,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one and also better than thenoyltrifluoroacetone and hexafluoroacetylacetone. The effect of various types of Lewis bases in combination with NMPP on the extraction of Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} has also been studied. A large synergistic enhancement was observed in both the cases with all the Lewis bases. Synergistic extraction constants, stability constants and the stoichiometry of the respective adducts formed during the extraction have been calculated.

4-Acylpyrazolones have been introduced for the first time by Jensen¹ for the solvent extraction of metals. Extraction of metals by 4-acylpyrazolones, especially 4-benzoyl-2,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one (BMPP) with or without addition of synergists has been reviewed². BMPP has proved to be a successful reagent for solvent extraction of metals and is more efficient than thenoyltrifluoroacetone (TTA) and hexafluoroacetylacetone (HFA) in most of the cases. It was considered worthwhile to study the extraction behaviour of the nitro derivatives of BMPP with respect to europium and neodymium. As the introduction of the nitro group is expected to lower its pK_a value, the extraction may occur at lower pH values than its parent compound, i.e. BMPP. The reagent 4(*p*)-nitrobenzoyl-2,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one (NMPP) was initially used for the solvent extraction of Cu, Co, Ni, Th³ and UO_2^{4+} in this laboratory.

The aim of the present work is to study the extraction of europium(III) and neodymium(III) with NMPP and compare its efficiency with BMPP, TTA and HFA. The effect of various organic Lewis bases, i.e. tri-*n*-butyl phosphate (TBP), tri-*n*-octyl phosphine oxide (TOPO) and dibenzyl sulphoxide (DBSO) in the extraction of Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} in combination with NMPP has also been investigated.

Experimental

NMPP was prepared¹ using 2,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one (MPP) and *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride. The reagent was recrystallised twice

from methanol and its purity was established by elemental analysis and m.p. data. The solutions of NMPP of requisite concentrations were prepared in toluene (A.R.).

Solution of Eu^{III} was prepared using the reagent grade Eu_2O_3 (99.9%; Fisons, Philadelphia), and Nd^{III} solution using $Nd(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (99.9%; Fluka), and the solutions were standardised gravimetrically. All other reagents used were of analytical grade.

A Varian 634 spectrophotometer and a Varian AA-475 atomic absorption spectrometer were used for the determination of Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} . pH was measured using a Elico pH meter.

Procedure for solvent extraction: The concentration of Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} in the aqueous phase was initially maintained at 3.3×10^{-4} and 3.5×10^{-4} M, respectively, and the ionic strength of the aqueous phase was maintained at 0.2 M (H, K)Cl. pH of the aqueous phase was measured after the extraction in all the experiments. Equal volumes (10 ml each) of pre-contacted aqueous phase and toluene phase containing the ligand NMPP were placed in stoppered pyrex glass bottles and shaken for 1 h in a thermostated mechanical shaker at $30 \pm 1^\circ$. The time for the equilibrium to reach in these systems was found to be 1 h. Concentrations of Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} were determined spectrophotometrically using alizarin red-S⁶, which was checked by determining the Eu^{III} content by atomic absorption spectrometry. The distribution ratios (K_d) of the metals in organic and aqueous phase were obtained. Experiments were carried out in duplicate

because K_d is found by ratio of concentration of metals obtained by difference.

Similar experiments were carried out to extract Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} with NMPP in combination with neutral oxo-donors, TBP, TOPO and DBSO and the distribution ratios were calculated.

Results and Discussion

The plots of $\log K_d$ vs pH at constant ligand concentration ($2 \times 10^{-2} M$) give a slope of three for both Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} indicating that three protons are released during the extraction. The slope value of the plot of $\log K_d$ vs $\log [\text{NMPP}]$ at constant pH is also 3 ± 0.1 for both Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} indicating that three moles of the ligand NMPP are involved in the formation of the extracted complexes (Fig. 1). Thus, the extraction equilibrium can be represented as

Fig. 1 Plots of $\log K_d$ vs $\log [\text{NMPP}]$: (●) Eu^{III} -NMPP system ($\text{pH}=1.5$) and (○) Nd^{III} -NMPP system ($\text{pH}=2$) in toluene: (●) Eu^{III} -NMPP, and (○) Nd^{III} -NMPP system.

where, HL represents the ligand NMPP and M refers to $\text{Eu}^{\text{s}+}$ and $\text{Nd}^{\text{s}+}$. The values of the equilibrium constant ($\log K_{\text{ex}}$) has been calculated by using the equation,

$$\log K_{\text{ex}} = \log K_d - 3 \text{pH} - 3 \log [\text{HL}]$$

The value of $\log K_{\text{ex}}$ is found to be -1.4 ± 0.1 for Eu^{III} -NMPP system and -1.6 ± 0.1 for Nd^{III} -NMPP system in toluene. The corresponding values for Eu^{III} -TTA⁸, Eu^{III} -BMPP⁷ and Eu^{III} -HFA⁸ systems are -11.86 , -3.96 and -5.79 . For Nd^{III} -TTA⁹, Nd^{III} -BMPP¹⁰ and Nd^{III} -HFA⁸ systems, the corresponding values of $\log K_{\text{ex}}$ are -8.38 , -5.63 and -6.15 . As the relative values of $\log K_{\text{ex}}$ under similar conditions provide an estimate

of the relative efficiency of the extraction with various ligands, it is clear that NMPP is a better ligand than BMPP, TTA and HFA for the extraction of Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} .

The effect of Lewis bases (S) in combination with the ligand NMPP on the extraction of Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} was studied by varying the concentration of the Lewis bases at constant pH and ligand concentration. This study gives information about the number of auxiliary ligands incorporated in the formation of adducts. Experiments conducted at constant auxiliary ligand concentration and pH with varying ligand concentration give information regarding the number of ligand molecules involved during the extraction in presence of Lewis bases. From the data, extraction equilibrium for the extraction of Eu^{III} and Nd^{III} in presence of auxiliary ligands may be shown as

where, $K_{\text{ex}'}$ refers to the extraction equilibrium constant. The values of $K_{\text{ex}'}$ and adduct stability constants ($\log K_s$) are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION CONSTANTS OF NMPP COMPLEXES OF Eu^{III} AND Nd^{III} AND ADDUCT FORMATION CONSTANTS

Auxiliary ligand	Eu^{III} -NMPP		Nd^{III} -NMPP	
	$\log K_{\text{ex}'}$	$\log K_s$	$\log K_{\text{ex}}$	$\log K_s$
TOPO	5.2 (± 0.1)	6.6	1.8 (± 0.1)	3.4
DBSO	0.9 (± 0.1)	2.3	0.7 (± 0.1)	2.3
TBP	0.8 (± 0.1)	2.2	0.8 (± 0.1)	2.4
—	-1.4 (± 0.1)	—	-1.6 (± 0.1)	—

Fig. 2 shows the plot of $\log K_d$ vs $\log [S]$ at constant pH and constant ligand concentration for

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log K_d$ vs $\log [S]$. Eu^{III} -NMPP system in toluene: (○) TOPO $5 \times 10^{-2} M$, $\text{pH}=1.4$, (△) DBSO $2 \times 10^{-2} M$, $\text{pH}=2.0$, and (●) TBP $5 \times 10^{-2} M$, $\text{pH}=1.6$.

TOPO, TBP and DBSO for Eu^{III} . The slopes indicate that two moles of TOPO and one mole each of TBP and DBSO take part in the adduct formation. In case of Nd^{III} , one mole each of TOPO, TBP and DBSO are taken up for adduct formation (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Plots of $\log K_d$ vs $\log (S)$, Nd^{III} -NMPP system in toluene: (○) TOPO 8×10^{-3} M, pH=2.0, (●) DBSO 8×10^{-3} M, pH=2.1, and (△) TBP 8×10^{-3} M, pH=2.0.

The results clearly indicate that synergistic enhancement occurs in these systems. The synergism with TOPO is higher than with TBP and DBSO which is probably due to its higher basicity.

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